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A STUDY ON ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURES AND DEVELOPMENT PROCESSES INVOLVED IN DESIGN DEVELOPMENT.

A CASE STUDY OF JAPANESE ELECTRONICS MANUFACTURES

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research is to clarify the element of organizational structure and development process involved in design development to achieve creating highly advanced, innovative design and establishing a coherent corporate design identity through making a deep analysis of cases in Japanese electronics manufactures. Therefore, through considering prior studies about product development and design management, this research extracts an analytical perspective to make analysis organizational structure and development process involved in design development. This research mainly describes two points. Firstly, this research describes organizational structures and development processes that two Japanese electronics manufactures adopt. Secondly, this research describes designers' communication with other department members and other designers in that organizational structures and development processes. Finally, this research makes analysis of these cases through the analysis perspective. As a result, this research finds out what natures of communications are needed among members in order to create highly advanced, innovative design and establish coherent corporate design identity. This research also finds out the element of organizational structure and development process to affect such communications among members.

Keywords: Management, Organizational Structure, Development Process

INTRODUCTION

The basic question addressed in this study is what organizational conditions are necessary for corporate

creation of highly advanced, highly innovative designs and a coherent corporate design identity.

With the emergence of mature markets, it has generally become difficult for corporations to maintain competitive superiority through differentiation based on factors such as function, quality, and price of product. This has heightened the importance of basic differentiation through creation of more advanced, more innovative designs. In this context, the terms "advanced" and "innovative" connote the creation and implementation of new concepts and designs that generate new customers and new markets.

Market maturation has also brought a lack of certainty about user needs. In attempting to deal with this uncertainty, corporations tend to concentrate on rapid, short-term development of broadly diversified products. This, however, results in markets that are engulfed in a bewildering variety of products and in shortened life cycles, all of which tends to increase user confusion (Shimaguchi and Ishii, 1989). In these circumstances, it is essential for a corporation to strengthen its corporate image by imbuing its products with an identity distinctive from that of other companies and maintaining this identity in all of its products. The corporation needs to create and consistently maintain a design identity that will help to strengthen the corporate brand.

The question then becomes what form of management the corporation should adopt to promote creation of such designs. It may be fairly said that business administration studies have heretofore left this question largely unanswered. In this light, we attempt to elucidate important conditions in organizational structure and design processes that support the creation of these

distinctive brand designs. Using two example cases in which corporations have developed and adopted design-related organizational structures and development processes that have effectively fostered creation of more highly advanced, we examine more highly innovative designs and developed more distinctive, coherent design identities.

As used in this study, the term “design” refers primarily to product design and in particular to the creation of ideas and concepts, the various activities performed for their materialization, and the objects in which they are embodied (i.e., the products).

CONSIDERATION OF PRIOR STUDIES AND EXTRACTION OF ANALYTICAL PERSPECTIVE

Treatises on product development generally discuss modes of management that increase efficiency in product development activities and improve product quality, and elucidate ways in which organizational structures and development processes may define the conduct and communication of organization members. They generally view product development as a process encompassing the transfer and integration within the organization of knowledge and information dispersed throughout it, and describe organizational structures and development processes that promote efficiency in that transfer and integration, as well as effective performance. They point out in particular the importance of designating a product manager who can effectively consolidate product development activities, mechanisms of promoting team member multitasking and interlinking among departments involved in the development, and closely coordinate the stages of development (Womack, Jones, and Roos, 1990; Clark and Fujimoto, 1991).

Design development activities, as seen from this viewpoint, take on added importance because they are intrinsically directed toward creating knowledge and embodying it in a tangible configuration (Utterback, 2006). For design development in an organized, systematic context, in particular, it is essential to transfer and consolidate information among the members, create new knowledge, and embody it in a single configuration.

Existing design management studies have also discussed management modes in light of these design activity characteristics.

In one such study, Lorenz (1990) points out the importance of providing for the inclusion of designers in product development from the early stages and the catalytic role designers play in connecting departments and adjusting coordination between them to create superior designs and achieve high performance. Dumas and Mintzberg (1989) posit the following as conditions for enabling the development of distinctive, coherent designs: (1) designation of a design champion; (2) establishment of a design policy and guidelines; (3) formulation of a program for design policy implementation (4) establishment of a design department and its exercise of leadership; and (5) a company-wide understanding of design. Dumas (1995) points out that in an organization in which members of various departments are involved, the creation of great designs must generally go through a complex process where a cross-functional group involved in the design interweaves various types of knowledge. It has been noted, moreover, that particularly for the creation of new knowledge at this group level, it is essential for the group members to mutually share and transfer knowledge (Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995), and highly desirable that this knowledge be multifaceted (Finke, Ward, and Smith, 1992).

It is evident that one of the basic principles for managing systematic design development is achieving a common understanding among all those involved in a design of user needs, behavior, perceptions, aesthetic emotions, and sensibilities. Further, holding this understanding of users characteristics, such as their sensibilities and perceptions, in common is an important condition for the creation of a coherent design identity. Lojacono and Zaccai (2004) noted the importance of “consumer-centered product design” that quickly and effectively absorbs the needs and knowledge of the users, shares them among its members, and reflects them in the designed product. Norman (1988) also noted the key need for designers to match the design product to user perceptions, which again suggests that in organized design development individual members must achieve a shared

understanding of user perceptions and a shared perception of the design they are developing.

As noted in these studies, mutual transfer and integration of team members' knowledge and information are important in creating highly advanced, highly innovative designs. From all of these studies, it is clear that how designers and other department members and the various designers themselves are interlinked and how they communicate has an important effect on this transfer and consolidation. To create a coherent design identity, moreover, it is important that the members involved hold perceptions and values relating to users and to the target design in common. The studies also clearly suggest that the nature of the interlinking and communication has an important influence on commonly held perceptions and values. In the case of Japanese manufacturers with over 100 in-house designers, interlinking and communication is particularly important because of the complexity of the transfer and consolidation of knowledge and information. Existing studies, however, are generally limited to conceptual discussions without empirical investigation, and thus do not show in concrete terms how organizational and development process factors affect relationships and communication among the various members.

In the present study, we focus on two corporations to investigate organizational structures and development processes involved in design development as important factors determining the nature of communication between the members, and the effects of differing organizational structures and development processes on this communication.

Figure.1 Analysis perspective

Source: This study

CASES

We consider two Japanese general electronics manufacturers (Companies A and B). Our study focus is the type of organizational structure and development process each has constructed to create

more highly advanced and innovative designs and coherent design identities, and the nature of the design activities that have emerged in that context.

These cases were selected specifically for the reason that these cases fit this research's question. The description of these cases is largely based on survey records from interviews done by author and secondary materials. Interviews were conducted three times for three persons from January to February 2011. Author interviewed for manager of design department in design center of company A, previous manager of design center of company A and manager of design center of company B.

1. Case 1 – Company A

Company A has long maintained a design center separate from its business units, with all design functions performed in that center and design work conducted there as requested by the business units. This longstanding centralized configuration contrasts with most Japanese general electronics manufacturers, where separate design departments are located within each of their divisions. At Company A, the design center sends designers to the corporate planning office to participate in work on corporate brand strategy and related tasks. In this way this configuration utilizes designers' competencies in formulating and maintaining corporate strategy.

Another characteristic of Company A's organizational structure relating to design is how the design center interacts with the business units. Within the design center, separate internal departments correspond with the business units. For business units X, Y, and Z, the design center is divided into design departments X, Y, and Z. In this configuration, each designer is able to gain a close understanding of the timing of model changes and other aspects of products to which he or she is assigned and becomes well informed about manufacturing productivity. This has enhanced efficient product development. Within the design center, moreover, each department head is responsible for controlling the design activities of that department, which has been effective in maintaining design integrity for products in the corresponding division.

This organizational framework, however, has also led to problems such as difficulty in creating

advanced, innovative designs, frequent changes in design tone, and difficulty in maintaining a consistent corporate design identity.

Company A originally chose the design center's departmental framework partly because designers' labor costs are allotted to the budgets of the respective business units. The end result, however, has been a strong tendency for each designer to work only for a single business unit. This has enabled a close interlinking among the designers within individual departments, but hampered interlinking between designers in different departments. In substance, the departmental framework has thus come to resemble that of different designers belonging to different business units, and has led to a strong tendency to concentrate on design work that stresses short development times and high efficiency. European and other designers reportedly view the designs of Company A as lacking unity, and within the company itself it has been said that its creation of advanced designs is insufficient.

To resolve these problems, requests have emerged in recent years for the establishment of regular meetings between design center head and top management. Efforts are in progress to increase the authority of the design center based on these meetings and discussions, and the company is working to actively encourage and increase the number of concepts and projects proposed by designers.

2. Case 2 – Company B

In Company B, until the latter half of the 1980s, the business units had their own design departments and design activities were performed within the business units. In this framework, designers in each business unit became highly familiar with the circumstances and conditions existing within that business unit, but they also developed a strong tendency to concentrate on short-term, efficient design development, leading to a situation that impeded creation of advanced, innovative designs. The designers' role, moreover, was largely limited to developing the styling and coloring of the products, since they were effectively assigned to specific plants within each business unit. The design effort was also characterized by the practice of designers, as a rule, being engaged in design for the same basic product category for many years, whether it was TVs,

PCs or other sectors. As a result, many of Company B's designs were derided as lacking refinement and being disparate, even within business units.

To resolve these problems, Company B embarked on a series of design-related organizational changes. Beginning in the 1990s, it established a design center and centralized its design functions. The role of the designers was also expanded to include visualization of the corporate philosophy, construction of new business image concepts, and design concept creation and proposal. As a result of these changes, designer competencies came to be utilized in corporate and business strategy formulation and implementation. In the 2000s, design functions were further consolidated and unified, and the design center became responsible for building the corporate brand identity.

At the same time, concern arose that this separation of the design function from the business units and its concentration in the design center would result in the loss of important advantages that had been gained by having designers embedded in the business units. More specifically, it was feared that the separation would impede the flow of useful user-related information that was available in on-site product development within the business units, and prevent its rapid incorporation into designs. Company B therefore devised and constructed a unique framework of mechanisms specifically designed to retain these advantages while enabling the development of highly advanced, highly innovative designs and a fostering a consistent design identity among all of its products.

Company B began by designating all of its designers as head office personnel and assigning them to positions as either head office staff or business unit staff. The business unit designers were physically placed in their respective business units and, as they were to be essentially engaged in the work of that business unit, their labor costs were allocated to business unit budgets. Nonetheless, each designer's personnel authority resided in the head office design center. With this configuration, Company B sought to maintain the advantages provided by the business unit system and maintain overall product development efficiency while enabling the design center to place each designer and invest resources in accordance with the overall

corporate-level design strategy it had formulated. In this way it became possible, for example, to allocate some designer resources from the TV and camera units to the refrigerator unit when necessary to strengthen its design development. It also facilitated application of design concepts and innovations developed in one product category to other products, and led to the creation of concepts and styling that could hardly have been imagined in the former business unit configuration. This mode of design development, interlinking designers from different backgrounds in various business units, has now become integral to everyday product design practices at Company B.

These mechanisms have proved highly effective in creating a coherent design identity for the whole corporation, as formulated and delineated in documentary form by the design center. Interpretation of this delineation naturally depends on the individual designers, and has led to a commonly shared understanding of the corporate design identity and its reflection in the products of each business unit through links between designers working together on product design in the business units. This is reinforced by including head office designers as participants in design development, who have on-site responsibility for products to adhere to the corporate design identity. In this way, the company has effectively established and maintained a coherent corporate and business unit design identity in the interplay between the head office and on-site design development.

At the same time, designers in the head office are actively encouraged to develop and propose advanced designs embodying new concepts, and to construct new mechanisms for their joint development. In this way, the company provides an environment in which designers stationed in the business units can, if necessary, link up with head office designers and engage in developing advanced designs in parallel with their engagement in the everyday work of the business units.

Another innovation at Company B is its establishment of “design directors” for product development projects. Design directors are charged by the design center to ensure full utilization of on-site designer capabilities in product development, with the mission of encouraging more creative design

activities and maintaining the integrity of the design identity. In Japanese corporations with divisional organizations, the business unit managers wield very strong authority over budgeting, operations, organization, and other phases of business unit management. They are usually drawn primarily from the sales and technical sectors, and are in many cases unfamiliar with the work of design. In Company B’s new configuration, design management resides with the design director and the business unit manager performs overall business unit management in consultation with the design director. The relationship between the design director and the business unit manager in regard to design development is one of equals. This effectively prevents unilateral modification or negation of designs by individual business unit managers.

With these innovations in organizational configuration and development process, Company B has effectively reconciled, at a high level, the sometimes conflicting requirements of everyday design development in the business units, where short development times and high efficiency are emphasized, and those of design development directed toward advanced and innovative design involving long design times. In this way, it has developed market-leading products based on previously nonexistent concepts while also achieving a coherent design identity across all its product areas.

DISCUSSION

1. Organizational structure – Independence of the design department

One important implication in both of these cases relating to organizational structure is that the design division (or the designers) being independent is indispensable for creating both highly advanced, innovative designs and a coherent design identity.

Each of the companies considered in this study maintains a “design center” as a department separate from its business units, encouraging its designers to actively participate in product development by securing the independence of the design department and strengthening its authority.

In a divisional organization, there is generally a strong tendency to attach importance to the short-term profits and goals of the individual units in order to fulfill its function as a single corporation

(Chandler, 1962). Accordingly, design development that is effective for short-term results and efficiency tends to be emphasized, and it becomes increasingly difficult to create advanced, innovative designs that generate new markets and user needs. In the overall corporate perspective, moreover, this environment tends to result in disparate design identities.

In Company B, as seen here, establishment of a design center, where designers are still actively engaged in product development enabled the designers to communicate with members of other departments on an equal basis and substantially reduced the designer passivity and compromise that had become rather prevalent in the divisional organization.

This clearly suggests that an organizational structure in which the design department is separated from the business units is conducive to designers being actively involved in product development and to the creation of advanced, innovative designs and a coherent design identity.

It is most important to note, however, that simply separating the design department from the business units is not in itself sufficient to secure the independence of the design department or change the modes of communication between the designers and the members of other departments.

This was clear in our consideration of Company A, which had for many years maintained a design center separate from its business units, but had been internally sectioned off in alignment with the business units, in part because designers' labor costs were allotted to the business unit budgets. As a result, business units' power had extended into the design department, making it difficult to maintain an environment conducive to designer-led design development. The business units, moreover, were strongly influenced by markets and logistics, which led to frequent changes in design identity.

In Company B, in contrast, vesting personnel authority in the design center enabled the allocation of designers in accordance with the corporate design strategy and helped to secure the independence of the design department. Its establishment of design directors also enabled design department leadership in management of design activities in each business unit and project.

These findings show that changing the organizational structure is not in itself sufficient to maintain design department independence. This independence must also be secured by some means of changing the nature of communications between the designers and other department members.

While securing design department independence, however, it is also essential to retain the advantages of having a design department in each business unit division. In design development within the units, it is possible to obtain a wealth of first-hand information on user needs and preferences that is only available on-site. If single-minded pursuit of highly advanced, highly innovative designs leads to a substantial decline in the efficiency of everyday design activities, it signifies that the means have been mistaken for the ends.

It was in this light that Company B established head office design staff designers and business unit staff designers with the two contingents mutually interlinked depending on need. The objective is an organizational structure and mechanism that fully utilizes the advantages of an independent design center but also retains the advantages of business unit-centered design.

2. Development process – Multifaceted interlinking of designers

Among the conditions for fostering creation of advanced, innovative designs together with maintaining a coherent design identity, the nature of the development process, as well as the organizational structure, is important in determining how designers communicate with each other. In the two cases under study, two different development process patterns are evident.

The first is a pattern of interlinking between designers charged with product designs in different business units. In Company B, the design center intentionally constructs mixed teams of designers engaged in the work of various units. This injects and merges various concepts and ideas within the teams and enables previously non-existent concepts and stylings to be created.

As noted by Dumas (1995) and Utterback (2006), design activity involves a complex interweaving of varieties of knowledge in a progression of problem solving. This implies that design activity is intimately related to knowledge and, in particular, that for

creating advanced, innovative designs via organized design activities by multiple designers, the process of knowledge and information transfer and consolidation between the designers is of primary importance (Dumas, 1995). This is based on the possibility of generating new knowledge through the interplay and merging of existing knowledge (Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995).

Design activity intrinsically involves the visualization of intermediate and final design objects. Visualization of these objects is itself a concrete expression of designer knowledge (Carlile, 2002; Utterback, 2006). In the visualization, observation, and modification of these objects, it is possible to gain knowledge from others and learn through comparison with one's own knowledge. In this way, the interaction generated by introducing visualized objects can effectively promote designers' mutual learning and creation of new knowledge. These visualizations and the mutual insights they offer to fellow designers, moreover, can promote the development of shared concepts and perceptions.

This communication (interaction) may therefore be viewed as conducive to the creation of advanced, innovative designs through its stimulation of mutual sharing and integration of knowledge and information held by the designers. It also supports the creation and maintenance of a coherent design identity based on this mutual integration. In this light, stimulating this kind of communication by configuring the development process to induce multiple links between different types of designers is very desirable.

The second development process pattern is one of interlinking head office staff designers and designers placed in hierarchal structures like those in business units.

In Company B, the head office staff designers actively propose new design concepts to the business units, and the head office and business units interlink and work together to develop them. This interlinking in a structure of higher and lower echelons evidently also induces the transfer and sharing of knowledge and information of different types and thus promotes the creation of advanced, innovative designs. In Company B, moreover, the head office designers also participate in routine design activities. They can thereby exert control

over the overall corporate design strategy and design identity. These links between higher and lower echelons evidently promotes the formation of mutually shared design perceptions and concepts, thereby contributing to the creation of a coherent design identity.

Figure2 Organizational structure and development process factors and communication among various members

Source: Author's creation

CONCLUSION

In the present study, by considering two Japanese general electronics companies, we have attempted to elucidate the organizational conditions that further the creation of advanced, innovative designs and a coherent design identity. In particular, we have focused on the communication between organization members in organized design activities and investigated the factors that may have important effects on that communication in organizational structures and development processes.

In this context, we were able to elucidate how organizational structure and development processes relating to design tend to define and regulate communication among members working together.

The factors described in this study, however, by no means represent all of the many issues that define the communication between organization members relating to design. Organized design activity is complex and dynamic, and its further explication will require a multidisciplinary approach, investigating a broad variety of cases to extract relevant factors and more detailed elucidation of their logical relationships.

REFERENCES

- Carlile, P. R. (2002) A Pragmatic View of Knowledge and Boundaries: Boundary Objects in New Product Development, *Organization Science*, vol.13, no.4, pp.442-455.
- Chandler, A. D. Jr. (1962) *Strategy and Structure*, MIT Press.
- Clark, K. and Fujimoto, T. (1991) *Product Development Performance: Strategy Organization and Management in the World Auto Industry*, Harvard Business School Press.
- Dumas, A. (1995) Commentary Reflections on Design and the Third Way, *Graham, P (edi): Mary Parker Follett, Prophet of Management*, the President and Fellows of Harvard College, pp 205-211.
- Dumas, A. and Mintzberg, H. (1989) "Managing Design Designing Management," *Design Management Journal*, Vol.1, pp37-44.
- Finke, R. A, Ward, T. B. and Smith, S. M. (1992) *Creative Cognition: Theory, Research, and Applications*, The MIT Press.
- Lojacono, G. and Zaccai, G. (2004) The Evolution of the Design-Inspired Enterprise, *Sloan Management Review*, vol.45, no.3, pp 75-80.
- Lorenz, C. (1990) *The Design Dimension: The New Competitive Weapon for Business*, Basil Backwell.
- Nonaka, I. and Takeuchi, H. (1995) *The Knowledge-Creating Company: How Japanese Companies Create the Dynamics of Innovation*, Oxford University Press.
- Norman, D.A. (2002) *The Design of Everyday Things*. New York, NY: Basic Books.
- Utterback, J. M. (2006) *DESIGN-INSPIRED-INNOVATION*, World Scientific Publishing.
- Womack, J., Jones, D. and Roos, D. (1990) *The Machine that Changed the World*, Rawson Associates.